

STUDIES ON THE CHANGES OF BLOOD-LIPOIDS OF NORMALLY FED AND VITAMIN C-DEFICIENT GUINEA-PIGS.

By BAIDYANATH GHOSH.

There is a significant rise in the cholesterol content of blood of guinea-pigs in vitamin C-deficiency.

Recent studies of the changes in the composition of blood and various tissues accompanying the onset of scurvy in guinea-pigs have not revealed striking changes. It has been shown by Ohata (*J. Biochem. Japan*, 1932, 16, 191) that there is a slight increase in acidity and fatty acid content. Recently, Tislowitz (*Z. Ges. Exper. Med.*, 1935, 97, 127) has shown that prolonged administration of vitamin C to dogs did not change the blood-cholesterol and he concluded that probably vitamin C has no direct influence on blood-cholesterol metabolism. Dogs, however, can synthesise their own vitamin C and it is likely that their blood ascorbic acid level has a constant value, so that prolonged administration of vitamin C may not appreciably increase this level and consequently any possible influence on blood-cholesterol metabolism by ascorbic acid may not be shown in experiments with dogs. In guinea-pigs, on the other hand, the vitamin C content of blood bears a close relationship to the ingested vitamin until the optimum dose of vitamin C is fed, when naturally the limiting value of ascorbic acid in blood is reached. It has, therefore, been considered desirable to study the effect of vitamin C on the blood lipoids, particularly cholesterol of guinea-pigs.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Male guinea-pigs weighing from 250-350 g. were fed on a basal diet consisting of powdered gram (20 parts), crushed oats (80 parts), salt (1 part), 2-3 drops of cod-liver oil and milk (30 c.c.) per animal, autoclaved for half an hour at 12 lb. pressure. Those receiving this diet alone rapidly declined in weight and developed typical scorbutic symptoms within 3 weeks. Another set of guinea-pigs was fed on germinated gram and green grass in sufficient quantities.

After 3 weeks the blood of the guinea-pigs (of both groups *i.e.*, those that were kept on scorbutic diet and those on normal diet) was drawn out from the heart and a measured quantity (2-3 c.c.) of blood was poured into a 50 c.c. measuring flask containing about 40 c.c. of alcohol-ether (3 : 1) mixture. The flask was gently warmed on a water-bath when it was gently rotated and as soon as the alcohol-ether mixture began to boil, it was removed

and cooled under the tap and finally made up to a definite volume with alcohol-ether mixture. This was filtered and the total lipid (*i.e.* 3 total fatty acid and cholesterol) was determined from a 20 c.c. aliquot. The alcohol-ether mixture was then saponified with sodium ethylate and evaporated on a water-bath. The last traces of alcohol were driven away by blowing a gentle current of air. The residue was then acidified with dilute sulphuric acid and the lipid matter was extracted by repeated boiling with petroleum ether. The petroleum ether extract was made up to a definite volume from which the total lipid was estimated by evaporation of the petroleum ether and by the chromate oxidation method described by Bloor (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1928, **77**, 53; see also Peters and Van Slyke, "Quantitative Clinical Chemistry" 1932, Vol. 2, 496). The results obtained are given in Table I.

The cholesterol content of the blood was determined from the same alcohol-ether extract. 10 C.c. of the alcohol-ether extract were evaporated to dryness on a water-bath; the dirty residue was extracted by boiling with 3 successive portions of chloroform (1 c.c. each). The extract was decanted to a glass stoppered graduated cylinder. The solution was cooled and was made up to 5 c.c. by addition of chloroform. To the chloroform solution prepared (5 c.c.) acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (0.1 c.c.) were added. In another similar cylinder a standard solution of cholesterol in chloroform (5 c.c.) was placed and acetic anhydride (1 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (0.1 c.c.) were added. The contents were thoroughly mixed and kept for 15 minutes to develop colour, which was compared in a colorimeter (Bloor, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1922, **52**, 191; Peters and Van Slyke, *loc. cit.*). The values of cholesterol content of blood are also shown in Table I.

TABLE I.

Guinea-pigs kept on scorbutic diet for 3 weeks.			Guinea-pigs kept on normal diet.		
	Mg. per 100 c.c. of blood.			Mg. per 100 c.c. of blood.	
Wt. of animals before drawing blood.	Total lipids.	Cholesterol.	Wt. of animals before drawing blood.	Total lipids.	Cholesterol.
214 g.	662.5	106	312 g.	625.0	58
189	562.5	90	405	687.5	58
244	500.0	83	350	506.3	60
250	675.0	74	350	506.3	80
265	421.8	80	420	599.5	62
299	875.0	80	400	687.5	60
264	675.0	113	390	537.5	66
222	500.6	121	360	450.0	90
284	675.0	117	440	562.5	66
Mean	616.3	96	Mean	573.4	66

Although the animals show fairly considerable individual variations with reference to the cholesterol and total lipid content of blood, it seems definite that in vitamin C-deficient guinea-pigs there is a rise of cholesterol content in blood, the average rise being of the order of 50%. It, therefore, seems possible that vitamin C has some influence on the cholesterol metabolism of blood. Taking the difference between the total lipoids and the cholesterol content as a measure of the total fatty acid content of blood it appears that this suffers no significant variation being $616.3-96 = 520.3$ in vitamin C-deficient and $573.4-66 = 507.4$ in normal condition.

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APPLIED CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA.

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